

PART 5

The benefits of a digitally-informed and empowered workforce

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In the first three articles of this series we looked at the tools that the construction sector could avail of to build a pathway to digitalisation success. The fourth detailed the need for upskilling in the industry, and this article will outline some of the benefits that the sector can secure if it continues to engage on this journey, writes Paul McCormack, Innovation Manager, Belfast Metropolitan College.

Construction in Ireland is experiencing significant internal challenges – labour shortages, supply chain problems and cost controls. These are compounded by external challenges such as the demand to reduce the construction CO2 footprint, and the energy consumption of buildings.

Despite strong pipelines of work (€1.64 trillion of construction-related turnover estimated for the EU market during the next five years), attracting young people into the sector is difficult, partly because of a perceived lack of stability, modernity and diversity in the sector. As detailed in previous articles, construction is one of the slowest to innovate, lying second last on the innovation table, just above the agricultural sector.

Innovate or perish

This lack of innovation has led to inefficiencies across the entire value chain and these inefficiencies have magnified as other sectors have embraced digitalisation ingrowth plans. These inherent, embedded inefficiencies,

in some places of endemic proportions, mean the industry must now innovate or perish. Innovation in digitalisation is the pathway to recovery, growth and sustainability. Cumulative inefficiencies not only result in increased costs, but also environmental impacts such as materials wastage, inefficient asset allocation, increased pollution and poor productivity. Today, many construction design processes are still being carried out that could be completed faster, cheaper and more accurately if the companies concerned embarked on a digital implementation strategy.

One of the fastest and most beneficial routes to address these challenges is to upskill the workforce, provide it with the digital skills, access and tools to help transition the sector into an innovative, relevant, energy efficient industry. These

benefits of digitalisation are many faceted and will be realised at all stages and levels of the construction value chain. They will also enable the sector to grow in expertise and remain competitive.

Addressing the panel discussion entitled “How BIM enables digitalisation and skills development” at RIAI’s Architecture + Building Expo 2021, Joseph Mady, founder and Managing Director, Digital Construction Technologies (DCT) and BIM Champion, CIF’s Mechanical & Electrical Contractors Association (M&ECA), said: “BIM is an interdisciplinary tool that all workers in construction require. Many will only need the BIM basics or fundamentals, while others will need more advanced knowledge. However, all will require the key knowledge and applications that empower digital utilisation for a company, society and environment to ultimately benefit from the ensuing cost, productivity and energy benefits that result.”

Opportunity

To meet the climate challenge, the construction sector must reduce its carbon footprint. This has resulted in the EU setting significant challenges that the construction sector must address. These challenges also bring opportunity. Companies that rise to them will grow, become more competitive and have a long-term future. Companies who fail to rise to the challenge will simply wither and die. To achieve these new international targets and enjoy the benefits of increased productivity,

competitiveness and economic growth, it is vital that the green economy delivers a better-skilled workforce and develops new competencies and methods of working.

Skills allocation

The pandemic has exacerbated the shortage of staff on construction sites across the supply chain to the sector. With productivity and safety at the top of all companies’ agendas, the use of digital tools and data analysis is the solution to maintaining safe numbers of staff on site, while also maintaining productivity. Digital planning and resourcing tools are key assets in assessing labour requirements on site and deploying staff across sites, thereby maximising efficiency and effectiveness.

In the same panel discussion at Architecture + Building Expo in November, Dr Avril Behan, Technological University Dublin, said: “As Europe seeks to address the climate crisis, construction must develop a skilled and digitally-equipped workforce. The green economy is a highly instrumental part of sustainable development and this provides a wonderful catalyst for the construction sector to deploy digital skills and innovative practices throughout the workforce, especially in the VET sector, and to equip all to become vocationally active.”

Digital efficiencies

As construction embraces Building Information Modelling (BIM) as one of the digital tools in its digitalisation toolbox, companies get into the generative design process that enables designers to explore thousands of possible designs in minutes. These BIM packages help designers access and develop key parameters early in the design phase, including cost, weight, design specifications, CO2 emissions, material wastage and much more as part of the design phase. This “automation” allows a company choose from optimal design outputs based on more precise, efficient and accurate designs. It also provides a framework on which to measure all parts of the construction phase, including cost, waste and energy consumption.

Digital project management tools are also highly effective throughout the entire planning and build process, assisting management to maintain a continuous digital “hands-on” approach, tracking data to make informed decision-making on materials, costs, productivity, planning and waste. Project planning using 3D scans to measure planned vs actual timelines allows for highly-accurate iterations and control measures. These digital advances have improved efficiencies by up to 50%.

Data analysis

BIM and digital twins provide continuous streams of data. This data, when translated into information, ensures that decisions are based on real-time information, enabling more thorough on-site and off-site inspections. In short, BIM is a digital representation of the physical and functional characteristics of a building ... it is the “digital twin” of the physical building and allows for inspection during and after construction. It also enhances post construction maintenance.

Michael Earley, BIM Manager at the DAA, was also at Architecture + Building Expo and he said: “Digitalisation is a vital process in our planning and asset management activities. We want to be smart clients who provide delivery teams with standards and processes that support the digital delivery of asset information. A key strategy for DAA is the integration of BIM, GIS and FM systems, each of which have their strengths but need to be integrated by using workflows to maximise benefits for the different functions within DAA. We are supporting the use of mobile devices for inspections, testing, commissioning, operations and maintenance which puts data provided by these technologies in the hands of the people who need it, wherever their work may be located.”

Connectivity

Digitalisation is now becoming pervasive in our daily lives. It is driving a level of connectivity never seen before in society. Construction companies that introduce and deploy digitalisation throughout their processes enjoy

significant benefits from increased connectivity. Utilising digital “disruptive” methods and technologies, such as BIM, enables staff, contractors and others in the supply chain to communicate electronically, exchange documents, and make immediate changes and revisions. Importantly, they can review building performance characteristics and share in the visual language tailored to different actors.

Michael Curran, Chairman, CIBSE Ireland and Head of Building Services, Energy & Utilities, NUIG reflected on this recently when he stated: “We are connected virtually to every part of the NUIG campus and can plan, monitor, evaluate and adjust all equipment. This saves time, money and energy. Digital connectivity, internally and externally to sub-contractors and operators, is key to the success of our effective energy management process.

Conclusion

For each company in the construction sector the digitalisation pathway will be unique and different, depending on size, scale and vision. For the journey to deliver benefits, the first step is to understand what it is you want from the process, and to then plan the route to unlocking the potential of your workforce.

As in other sectors, success and growth for companies in the built environment is built upon staff. If the staff are well-trained and skilled in their work, they become more connected and engaged. They will become more involved and enthusiastic about their work and, as a result, productivity and quality levels will increase.

A digitally-informed and empowered construction workforce will drive innovation and growth in the sector. It will ensure that it can adapt, modernise and embrace new technology, and truly adopt digital working as the new standard. This will help individual companies and the sector at large to overcome inherent resistance to change. The key benefit of digitalisation is an empowered, skilled workforce that can build better, greener and more sustainable buildings. ■

Paul McCormack with Michael Curran, Avril Behan, Michael Earley and Joseph Mady.